

ARMADILLO

Enhancing

forensic evidence collection

Ensuring

privacy

Supporting

the prevention of drug-facilitated sexual assaults

Contact Us

For more information, visit our website:

armadillo-project.eu

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Project Partners

ARMADILLO is a consortium of 17 key partners, including leading academic institutions, research organizations, and industry leaders from across Europe. The consortium includes:

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